

D6.1 - Guidelines on planned actions to gendering research & teaching

WP6 - Gendering Research & Teaching

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MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Information in this report that may influence other MINDtheGEPs tasks

Linked task	Suggested recommendations
T6.1 Increase gender awareness in research content and funding Increase gender sensitivity in research funding procedures	<p>4.1 Recommendation 1: Including sex/gender in your research ideas phase</p> <p>4.2 Recommendation 2: Gender sensitive proposal writing</p> <p>4.3 Recommendation 3: Implementing sex/gender within your research and research team</p> <p>4.4 Recommendation 4: Gender sensitive dissemination phase</p> <p>4.5 Recommendation 5: General – how to be a gender-aware researcher</p>
T6.2 Increase gender equality in team composition and leadership	
T6.3 Increase gender sensitivity in research funding procedures	
T.6.4 Gendering scientific publications	
T.6.5 Increase gender sensitivity in teaching for a long-term effect	
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	3.3 Recommendation 5: Course evaluation including both teachers' and students' input
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1. Introduction: MINDtheGEPs project

MINDtheGEPs takes a multidisciplinary multidimensional approach to challenging gender imbalances across five different countries with still traditional gender regimes (Italy, Spain, Serbia, Ireland, Poland) and across various types of RPOs: 4 public universities (Turin, Tralee, Gdansk, Jagiellonian) and 1 public non-academic research institute (CNR); 1 academic (Belgrade) and 1 private technological institute centre (Galicia). The consortium, led by the University of Turin's CIRSDe, comprises also three non-implementing organisations bringing complementary expertise in monitoring and evaluation (Knowledge and Innovation), research communication (Uppsala University) and scientific publishing (Elsevier). In order to promote systemic institutional change and following the "no data-no policy" principle, the project will map the existing data and, building on the tools developed within an ongoing research project of the project coordinator, will produce new qualitative-quantitative evidence. On this basis, both structural and cultural actions can be effectively designed. At a cultural level, the project will organise a virtuous chain of training, starting from across-partners "train the trainers" workshops to within-partners laboratories addressed to young women, but endorsing the approach of "fixing the system not the women", also to men and senior researchers. At structural level, the project will introduce work-family measures addressed also to men, equality targets in decision-making boards and gender-sensitive research. The establishment of proper figures and bodies creates conditions for the endurance of GEPs beyond the project's life. A multidisciplinary team (also including key-persons in middle or top management), coupled with a multi-skilled Advisory Board (including relevant national authorities), and 4 professional associations both in STEM and SSH, will contribute to a successful change in RPOs and in society at large.

1.1 Introduction and objectives of the deliverable

The overall objectives of deliverable 6.1 are:

- 1) Increase gender awareness in **research content and funding**
- 2) Increase gender equality in **team composition and leadership**
- 3) Increase gender sensitivity in **research funding procedures**
- 4) Gendering scientific publications
- 5) Increase **gender sensitivity in teaching** for a long-term effect

In this particular deliverable, basing ourselves on desk research, our own expertise, all MTG partners experiences and existing guidelines we have prepared a set of overall recommendations supporting academic and non-academic organizations to foster the emphasis and awareness of gender issues across teaching and research. Our guidelines on planned actions to gender research and teaching take a form of a certain checklist – **it is a user friendly and concise toolbox** assisting organizations in following gender mainstreaming.

2. Methodology

To facilitate the work of trainers and academics and offer good recommendations in training across academia (including gender equality issues) and in conducting gender aware research it is important to follow a certain **check-list** helping organizations contextualizing their research and teaching in diversity and inclusion paradigms.

The way we have collected this information has been through five different sources:

1. Indications taken from previous tasks carried out within the framework of the MINDTHEGEPs project itself such as indications arising from the state-of-the-art review in T2.1 “State of the art review” or the narratives given in T2.6 “Qualitative analysis: interviews with male and female researchers at different grades, across all dimensions” among others.
2. Inputs from other projects oriented towards gender equality (such as GE Academy, GEA-Gendering academia, R&I PEERS, CALIPER, FESTA, GENERA, etc.)
3. Experience and existing actions from consortium partners. The MINDtheGEPs consortium consists of 10 different partners, each of them with a different form of organisation and with different initiatives implemented that can serve as feedback within the consortium itself to obtain ideas of good practices.
4. Additional materials provided by desk research, not only related to EU Gender Equality projects but any organisation that has been able to add value in some way in aspects related to gender equality.
5. Lessons learned through MINDtheGEPs workshops and activities. For example, at the “Train the trainers”, a two-day training workshop to build capacity for sustainable change in partner organisations. Between 7-8 June, around 50 people met in Vigo (Spain) to discuss basic concepts and tools to promote organisational change, and how situated knowledge can support the implementation of gender equality plans.

The combination of all these tools served as indications to follow in order to develop the core of this deliverable, ***Guidelines on planned actions to gender research and teaching*** for research organisations (academic and non-academic).

3. Recommendations for gendering teaching

Recommendation 1	Defining gender-sensitive competences to be developed during teaching
Recommendation 2	Providing academic teachers with a proper diversity & inclusion training
Recommendation 3	Tailoring the course content to the competence development and diversity & inclusion standards
Recommendation 4	Conducting the course
Recommendation 5	Course evaluation including both teachers and students input

3.1 Recommendation 1: **Defining gender-sensitive competences to be developed during teaching**

- ✓ Capacity to analyse from a gender perspective in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Critical reading of standard texts and information in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Working within a non-androcentric analytical framework in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Capacity to analyse biases in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ To become aware of the ideological role of biases.
- ✓ To become aware of inequalities between women and men and among women themselves.
- ✓ Capacity to identify gender inequalities occurring in the subject in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Understanding of such inequalities in relation to gender issues, especially to those linked to the sexual division of labour.
- ✓ Understanding of and capacity to work with non-androcentric statistics.
- ✓ Capacity to analyse policies from a gender perspective.
- ✓ **The competences are to be added to the general expectations for a given positions (concerns all career levels)**

3.2 Recommendation 2: **Providing academic teachers with a proper diversity & inclusion training**

- ✓ Possibility for academic teacher/tutor/promotor/coach to participate in the training on gender biases & diversity & inclusion organized by own institution.
- ✓ Venue, time and program: taking into consideration diversity & inclusion of participants.
- ✓ Anti-bias components are crucial during such training, such as increasing one's awareness of pervasiveness of biases and overcoming them.
- ✓ Conflict and diversity management during the class an important part of such training.

- ✓ Use didactic methods that will allow you to develop a deep understanding of the impact of gender constructs on the lives of listeners and the development of science.
- ✓ Referring to the life experiences of students, indicating didactic examples, remember to maintain equality, i.e. include the "gender" category and gender experience.

3.3 Recommendation 3: Tailoring the course content to the competence development and diversity & inclusion standards

- ✓ Possibility for academic teacher/tutor/promotor/ of gender sensitive review of the syllabus.
- ✓ Getting to know a non-androcentric analytical framework in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Getting to know a non-androcentric analytical framework in the respective field of the researcher-academic.
- ✓ Getting to know and overtraining ways of communicating that will be sensitive to gender differences.
- ✓ Getting to know didactic methods that will allow you to deepen the awareness and knowledge about the impact of gender on learning and solving scientific / social problems among students.
- ✓ Consciousness about biases in the respective field analysed during the course.
- ✓ Identification of gender inequalities occurring in the subject.
- ✓ Understanding of and capacity to work with non-androcentric statistics.

3.3 Recommendation 4: Conducting the course

- ✓ Remember what has been found on the phenomenon/problem to be investigated and whether the studies analyse how the category of "gender" research in the field.
- ✓ Mention the scale of the phenomenon/problem in women and men.
- ✓ Plan and develop multidisciplinary bibliographic strategies when searching for information on the research problem/topic and the methodologies used in its study.
- ✓ Bear in mind the contributions of both women and men to scientific knowledge on the research topic.
- ✓ Be careful to avoid using androcentric and/or sexist language. Do not use masculine forms as a generic universal. Specifically name women where appropriate. Introduce the term and examples of mansplaining.
- ✓ Avoid essentialist terms, such as *"disability", "cardiopathic", "obese", "a mentally ill person" etc.* Try to use phrases like: *a person living with disability or functional diversity; a person living with heart disease; a person living with obesity, a person with an experience of a mental crisis etc.*
- ✓ Use empowering language. Avoid language tinged with judgements, such as: *a person suffering from Down Syndrome, a single mother, illegal migrant, a victim.* Try to use neutral or empowering phrases like: *a person with Down Syndrome, an independent mother, a person*

with migrant experience/a person asking for asylum/a person seeking for humanitarian protection, a person experiencing discrimination.

- ✓ Be sensitive to word phrase hierarchy (*avoid putting any version always first*)
- ✓ Avoid gendered stereotypes as descriptive terms: like ladylike handshake, to throw/cry like a girl, boys don't cry
- ✓ Avoid using stereotypical images in order to be gender-inclusive. Try to have more than one person in a chosen image (instead of e.g. doctors as male and nurses as female; kindergarten teachers as female only)
- ✓ Avoid using “man” as the neutral term (mankind versus humankind; To a man versus to every person) or “he” to refer to unknown (removing women from the common experience).
- ✓ Do not use the term “gender” as a synonym for “sex”, because **sex** is a biological quality or classification of sexually-reproducing organisms (generally female, male, and/or intersex), while gender is a socio-cultural process that refers to cultural and social attitudes that together shape and sanction “feminine” and “masculine” behaviours, products, technologies, environments, and knowledges. Very important is to have in mind that gender does not necessarily match sex.
- ✓ Avoid patronizing language which promotes trivialization (Darling, Love; referring to adult women as “girls” or using the word “woman” dismissively)
- ✓ When conducting seminars, exercise and project classes, remember to maintain diversity (due to culture, age and gender) in student teams.

3.3 Recommendation 5: **Course evaluation including both teachers and students input**

- ✓ A standard section (1-2 questions) in course evaluation to confirm gender sensitivity of the course should be prepared by the institution.
- ✓ Ex:
 - How the content of the course applies to the standards of gender sensitivity? 1-5
 - How the academic teacher/tutor/promotor/coach fits into the standards of gender sensitivity? 1-5
 - Have you felt that diverse opinion have been encouraged and included during the discussions presented in the course? 1-5
 - Has the academic teacher/tutor/promotor/coach presented all genders perspective during the course? 1-5
 - Has gender sensitive language been used and promoted during the course and within the course materials? 1-5

4. Recommendations for gendering research

Recommendation 1	Including sex/gender in your research ideas phase
Recommendation 2	Gender sensitive proposal writing
Recommendation 3	Implementing sex/gender within your research and research team
Recommendation 4	Gender sensitive dissemination phase
Recommendation 5	General – how to be a gender-aware researcher

4.1 Recommendation 1: Including sex/gender in your research ideas phase

Checklist:

- ✓ Have you considered how assessments of sex/gender, including stereotypes about what is considered “female” or “male”, can affect what you want to investigate, what questions you ask and how to answer them?
- ✓ Is sex/gender important for understanding the phenomenon you will investigate, and if so, how? Are there other dimensions that can be considered in relation to sex/gender, such as age, ethnicity, educational level, income, occupation, geographical location or technical competence?
- ✓ Have you reviewed literature and other sources relating to sex/gender in the research field?

4.2 Recommendation 2: Gender sensitive proposal writing

- ✓ Mention whether scientific knowledge with a gender perspective has been found on the phenomenon/problem to be investigated and whether the studies analyse how the category of “gender” research in the field.
- ✓ Mention the scale of the phenomenon/problem in women and men
- ✓ Plan and develop multidisciplinary bibliographic strategies when searching for information on the research problem/topic and the methodologies used in its study.
- ✓ Bear in mind the contributions of both women and men to scientific knowledge on the research topic.

- ✓ Remember about gender-sensitive hypotheses and objectives
- ✓ The objectives need to be set within specific social and historical contexts.
 - The hypotheses should not refer to one sex if the aim is to generalize.
 - If the hypotheses do refer to only one sex, the reasons should be indicated and justified.
 - Take into account the influence of cultural, social and economic factors.
 - Prepare research questions challenging gender biases

Checklist:

- ✓ Does the project's research topics and methods take the sex/gender dimension into account? Does the proposal explain how the sex/gender dimension will be handled?
- ✓ Are researchers trained in gender studies included in the research group?
- ✓ Have you considered whether the results of the research can have different effects on women and men, boys or girls? Can the research contribute to the advancement of gender equality?

4.3 Recommendation 3: Implementing sex/gender within your research

4.3.1 Methodology - Quantitative study:

4.3.1.1 Sample:

- ✓ It is crucial for the sample to be stratified by sex and age group.
- ✓ It is also important to take into account groups in a situation of vulnerability and other significant socioeconomic characteristics.
- ✓ Avoid gender biases in inclusion and exclusion criteria.

4.3.1.2 Variables:

- ✓ The variables that are used must highlight the existence of the relationship between Your topic/issue being studied and gender factors.
- ✓ Include variables that reflect the diversity between women and men as groups and therefore any gender factors.

4.3.1.3 Questionnaires:

- ✓ Disaggregate the data by sex and other axes of stratification.
- ✓ Include variables that help to identify gender inequalities in health (e.g. the ratio between paid and unpaid work).
- ✓ Include items to measure the specific health situations of women and men.
- ✓ Ensure that any items in questionnaires are understandable and relevant for women and men.

4.3.2 Methodology - Qualitative study:

- ✓ Include profiles of people representative of different situations and experiences in relation to the research phenomenon/problem.
- ✓ Deciding which tools to use will require preliminary analysis to identify any gender biases that might affect the data gathering tools; assess whether they combine information on women and men; analyse the context where and when they have been used and whether they are validated for both sexes;

4.3.2.1 Tools:

- Semi-structured or in-depth interviews:
 - Ask questions common to women and men in order to compare data.
 - Collect data on questions specific to women and men and give interpretations and perceptions of the data.
 - Include questions to measure the specific health situations of women and men, and the health situations common to both sexes.
- Group interviews:
 - Select groups made up of women and men to find out about their specific discourses.
- Observational methods:
 - Pay attention to gender roles and stereotypes and any differences between women and men.

4.3.3 Results and discussion

- It is important to disaggregate the data by sex.
- To reflect social heterogeneity, it is also important to be able to disaggregate the data by age groups, social stratification and other factors.
- In the results and discussion, show the situations and experiences of women and men in relation to the research phenomenon/problem.
- Include data that reflect the interaction with other relevant variables. Do not focus only on certain inequalities in isolation, because they can mask other inequalities, such as age, ethnic origin and social class.

Checklist:

- ✓ Are research methods, such as questionnaires, focus groups, etc., designed in a way that considers possible sex/gender differences and similarities between gender? Will sex/gender-differentiated data be collected? Have you ensured that samples, test groups or other involved in the project are diverse in terms of sex/gender, age and other background variables?
- ✓ Will sex/gender be a variable in the analysis? Will other variables be included in relation to sex/gender in the analysis?
- ✓ Are unconscious (stereotypical) assumptions about sex/gender implicit in the interpretation of data? Are there dimensions other than sex/ gender that are important to consider?

4.4 Recommendation 4: Gender sensitive dissemination phase

Checklist:

- ✓ Is the sex/gender dimension included in the presentation of findings?
- ✓ If the sex/gender dimension is included, is it done in a way that does not reproduce stereotypical notions about gender, but also looks at variations within the gender categories?
- ✓ Have you considered that dissemination of the research findings can be directed towards networks, institutions, journals and conferences that address gender issues?

4.5 Recommendation 5: General – how to be a gender-aware researcher

- ✓ Give consideration to biases in order to avoid errors in the selection of the sample, the analysis of results and the formulation of conclusions.
- ✓ With respect to the language used:
 - Be careful to avoid using androcentric and/or sexist language.
 - Do not use masculine forms as a generic universal. Specifically name women where appropriate
 - Avoid essentialist terms, such as “disability”, “cardiopathic”, “obese”, etc. Try to use phrases like: *a person living with disability or functional diversity; a person living with heart disease; a person living with obesity, etc.*
 - Do not use the term “gender” as a synonym for “sex”, because sex is a biological quality or classification of sexually-reproducing organisms (generally female, male, and/or intersex), while gender is a socio-cultural process that refers to cultural and social attitudes that together shape and sanction “feminine” and “masculine” behaviours, products, technologies, environments, and knowledges. Very important is to have in mind that gender does not necessarily match sex.
- ✓ When creating your team make sure you attract diverse talents with regard to gender, age, culture, and other factors.

References & further reading

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<https://www.vives.org/programes/publicacions/publicacions-xarxa-vives/descarrega-de-les-publicacions/>

GENDER INNOVATIONS; Methods of Sex, Gender, and Intersectional Analysis
<http://genderedinnovations.stanford.edu/methods-sex-and-gender-analysis.html>